

In Vitro Antifungal Potential of *Morganella morganii* and Determination of its Chemical Composition by Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry

Sabreen A Kamal

Department of Biology, College of Science for women, University of Babylon, Iraq

Available Online: 25th April, 2017

ABSTRACT

Bioactives were analyzed using gas chromatography-mass spectroscopy (GC-MS) techniques, then the in vitro antibacterial and antifungal activity of the methanolic extract was evaluated. GC-MS analysis of *Morganella morganii* revealed the existence of the Tricyclo[4.3.1.1(3.8)]undecan-1-amine, 3-Methoxybenzaldehyde semicarbazone, carboxaldehyde, 1-methyl-,oxime, (Z)-(+), 1,5,5-Trimethyl-6-methylene-cyclohexene, 4-(2,5-Dihydro-3-methoxyphenyl)butylamine, Paromomycin, 9-Borabicyclo[3.3.1]nonane, 9-mercapto-, Benzenemethanol, 2-(2-aminopropoxy)-3-methyl, Acetamide, N-(6-acetylaminobenzothiazol-2-yl)-2-(adamantan, rin-6-carboxylic acid, 4-(2,5-Dihydro-3-methoxyphenyl)butylamine, N-(2,5-Dicyano-3,4-dihydro-2H-pyrrol-2-yl)-acetamide, 3,10-Dioxatricyclo[4.3.1.0(2,4)]dec-7-ene, 3-Cyclohex-3-enyl-propionic acid, Eicosanoic acid, phenylmethyl ester, 3,7-Diazabicyclo[3.3.1]nonane, 9,9-dimethyl-, Dithiocarbamate, S-methyl-,N-(2-methyl-3-oxobutyl)-, dl-Homocysteine, 2-(2-Furyl)pyridine, 1,7-Dioxa-10-thia-4,13-diazacyclopentadeca-5,9,12-trione, 5,7-Dodecadiyn-1,12-diol, 1-(β -D-Arabinofuranosyl)-4-O-difluoromethyluracil, Uric acid, Pyrrolo[1.2-a]pyrazine-1,4-dione, hexahydro-,12-Methyl-oxa-cyclododecan-2-one, Phthalic acid, butyl undecyl ester, 9,12,15-Octadecatrienoic acid, 2,3-bis(acetyloxy)propyl ester, 1,2,4-Trioxolane-2-octanoic acid 5-octyl-, methyl ester, 12-Dimethylamino-10-oxododecanoic acid, Octahydrochromen-2-one, L-Aspartic acid, N-glycyl-,2H-Oxecin-2-one, 3,4,7,8,9,10-hexahydro-4-hydroxy-10-meth, Thiazolo[4,5-d]pyrimidine-5,7(4H,6H)-dione, 2-amino-4-(2-ph, Dec-9-en-6-oxo-1-ylamide, 3,6,12-Trimethyl-1,4,7,10,13,16-hexaaza-cyclooctadecane, 2-IodoHistidine, 2,5-Piperazinedione, 3,6-bis(2-methylpropyl)-, 9-Octadecenamide, (Z)-, 3',8,8'-Trimethoxy-3-piperidyl-2,2'-binaphthalene-1,1',4,4'-tetra. *Citrullus colocynthis* (Crude) was very highly active (6.39 \pm 0.27) mm. The results of anti-fungal activity produced by *Morganella morganii* showed that the volatile compounds were highly effective to suppress the growth of *Aspergillus terreus* (5.613 \pm 0.23). *Morganella morganii* produce many important secondary metabolites with high biological activities. Based on the significance of employing bioactive compounds in pharmacy to produce drugs for the treatment of many diseases, the purification of compounds produced by *Morganella morganii* can be useful.

Keywords: Antifungal and antibacterial activity, *Morganella morganii*, GC-MS, Secondary metabolites.

INTRODUCTION

This bacterium came to be known as Morgan's bacillus and was later classified as *Bacillus morganii*¹⁻³. *Morganella* are motile, non-lactose fermenting gram-negative bacteria, which share with *Proteus* the capacity for urease production and presence of phenylalanine deaminase. *Morganella* are motile, non-lactose fermenting gram-negative bacteria, which share with *Proteus* the capacity for urease production and presence of phenylalanine deaminase⁴⁻⁶. *Morganella* species are infrequent causes of disease in healthy individuals. Clinical infections due to *M. morganii* often involve the urinary tract, skin and soft tissue and hepatobiliary tract⁷⁻⁹. Urinary tract infection is the most common clinical infection site. Most often these occur in elderly patients in nursing homes with long-term indwelling catheters¹⁰. *Morganella* is the fifth leading cause of UTIs in nursing home patients¹¹⁻¹³.

Morganella usually causes skin and soft tissue infections. Falagas reported thirteen patients (54%) suffered from skin and soft tissue infections in a 4-year period at Greece hospital¹⁴.

Morganella morganii was originally thought to be a cause of summer diarrhea. The organism has been isolated along with *Proteus mirabilis* more frequently in patients with diarrhea than in healthy controls¹⁵. *M. morganii* is found in the environment and in the intestinal tracts of humans, mammals, and reptiles as part of the normal flora¹⁶. *Morganella* has been reported as the cause of up to 3% of bacteremias in a nursing home, arising primarily from either the urinary tract or soft tissue infections¹⁷. *Morganella* could also cause intra-abdominal infections. The portals of entry of *M. morganii* bacteremia involved hepatobiliary tract was 22% by Lee report during one-year period¹⁸. In a retrospective review of sixty one cases of *M. morganii*

Table 1: Bioactive chemical compounds identified in methanolic extract of *Morganella morganii*.

<p>Tricyclo[4.3.1.1(3.8)]undecan-1-amine RT= 3.150 Mw=165.15175 Pharmacological activity: anti-viral activity</p>	<p>3-Methoxybenzaldehyde semicarbazone RT=3.396 Mw=193.085127 Pharmacological activity: anti-malarial, anticancer, antibacterial, antifungal</p>	<p>carboxaldehyde, 1-methyl-, oxime, (Z)-(+) RT=3.613 Mw=139.099714 Pharmacological activity: antimicrobial activity</p>
<p>1,5,5-Trimethyl-6-methylene-cyclohexene RT=3.996 Mw=136.1252 Pharmacological activity: antioxidant, antimicrobial</p>	<p>4-(2,5-Dihydro-3-methoxyphenyl)butylamine RT=4.191 Mw=181.146665 Pharmacological activity: antifungal, antibacterial, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant</p>	<p>Paromomycin RT=4.489 Mw=615.296303 Pharmacological activity: Antimicrobial activity</p>
<p>9-Borabicyclo[3.3.1]nonane, 9-mercapto- RT=4.654 Mw=154.098752 Pharmacological activity: anti-fungal activity</p>	<p>Benzenemethanol aminopropoxy)-3-methyl RT=4.878 Mw=195.125929 Pharmacological activity: antifungal, antibacterial, anti-inflammatory</p>	<p>Acetamide, N-(6-acetylamino-2-yl)-2-(adamantan RT=4.986 Mw=281383.166748 Pharmacological activity: antiarthritic, anti-inflammatory</p>
<p>Pterin-6-carboxylic acid RT=5.759 Mw=207.039239 Pharmacological activity: Anti-cancer, anti-viral, anti-HIV, anti-protozoal</p>	<p>4-(2,5-Dihydro-3-methoxyphenyl)butylamine RT=5.776 Mw=181.146665 Pharmacological activity: anti-oxidant</p>	<p>N-(2,5-Dicyano-3,4-dihydro-2H-pyrrol-2-yl)-acetamide RT=5.799 Mw=176.069811 Pharmacological activity: anti-fungal activity</p>

3,10-Dioxatricyclo[4.3.1.0(2,4)]dec-7-ene
RT=5.822
Mw=138.06808
Pharmacological activity: anti-inflammatory, analgesic and antipyretic

3-Cyclohex-3-enyl-propionic acid
RT=5.845
Mw=154.09938
Pharmacological activity: anti-fungal activity

Eicosanoic acid, phenylmethyl ester
RT=6.348
Mw=402.349781
Pharmacological activity: anti-bacterial activity

3,7-Diazabicyclo[3.3.1]nonane, 9,9-dimethyl-
RT=6.566
Mw=154.146998
Pharmacological activity: antiarrhythmic activity

Dithiocarbamate, S-methyl-,N-(2-methyl-3-oxobutyl)-
RT=6.817
Mw=191.043856
Pharmacological activity: anti-bacterial activity

dl-Homocysteine
RT=7.813
Mw=135.035399
Pharmacological activity: Anti-tumor Activity

2-(2-Furyl)pyridine
RT=7.933
Mw=145.052764
Pharmacological activity: anti-inflammatory, anthelmintic,

1,7-Dioxa-10-thia-4,13-diazacyclopentadeca-5,9,12-trione
RT=9.003
Mw=276.077993
Pharmacological activity: Unknown

5,7-Dodecadiyn-1,12-diol
RT=9.438
Mw=194.13068
Pharmacological activity: anti-fungal activity

1-(β-d-Arabinofuranosyl)-4-O-difluoromethyluracil
RT=12.528
Mw=294.066343
Pharmacological activity: anti-viral or anti-cancer activity

Uric acid
RT=12.814
Mw=168.02834
Pharmacological activity: anti-gout activity

Pyrrolo[1.2-a]pyrazine-1,4-dione, hexahydro-
RT=13.295
Mw=154.074227
Pharmacological activity: antioxidant activity

12-Methyl-oxa-cyclododecan-2-one

RT=14.033

Mw=198.16198

Pharmacological

Antibacterial Activity

activity:

Phthalic acid, butyl undecyl ester

RT=14.067

Mw=376.26136

Pharmacological

antitumoral

activity:

9,12,15-Octadecatrienoic acid, 2,3-bis(acetyloxy)propyl ester

RT=14.245

Mw=436.28249

Pharmacological

activity: anti-microbial and anti-inflammation

1,2,4-Trioxolane-2-octanoic acid 5-octyl-, methyl ester

RT=14.565

Mw=344.256275

Pharmacological

bacterial activity

activity:

anti-bacterial activity

12-Dimethylamino-10-oxododecanoic acid

RT=14.948

Mw=257.199093

Pharmacological

activity

Octahydrochromen-2-one

RT=15.343

Mw=154.09938

Pharmacological

activity: antiviral, fungicidal, antiprotozoal and antiplatelet activities

L-Aspartic acid, N-glycyl-

RT=15.452

Mw=190.058971

Pharmacological

activity: anti-cancer

2H-Oxecin-2-one, 3,4,7,8,9,10-hexahydro-4-hydroxy-10-methyl-

RT=15.532

Mw=184.109944

Pharmacological

activity

activity:

Antibacterial activity, Antifungal activity

Thiazolo[4,5-d]pyrimidine-5,7(4H,6H)-dione, 2-amino-4-(2-phenyl-ethyl)-

RT=15.921

Mw=288.068096

Dec-9-en-6-oxo-1-ylamide

RT=16.087

Mw=183.125929

Pharmacological

antistaphylococcal activity

activity:

3,6,12-Trimethyl-1,4,7,10,13,16-hexaaza-cyclooctadecane

RT=16.465

Mw=384.175732

Pharmacological

activity: Unknown

2-Iodo-L-histidine

RT=16.682

Mw=280.966125

Pharmacological

activity: anti-cancer activity

2,5-Piperazinedione
3,6-bis(2-methylpropyl)-
RT=17.477
Mw=226.168128
Pharmacological activity: anti-fungal activity

,3,6-bis(2-
9-Octadecenamide, (Z)-
RT=17.907
Mw=281.271864
Pharmacological activity: Anti-microbial

3',8,8'-Trimethoxy-3-piperidyl-2,2'-
binaphthalene-1,1',4,4'-tetra
RT=20.018
Mw=487.163101
Pharmacological activity: Unknown

Table 2: Antifungal activity of *Morganella morganii* metabolite products.

Fungi	Antibiotics / <i>Morganella morganii</i> metabolite products			
	<i>Morganella morganii</i> metabolite products	Amphotericin B	Fluconazol	Miconazole nitrate
<i>Microsporium canis</i>	2.681±0.17 ^a	1.004±0.03	3.601±0.17	2.972±0.16
<i>Candida albicans</i>	4.551±0.21	4.703±0.20	2.852±0.15	2.200±0.14
<i>Saccharomyces cerevisiae</i>	4.100±0.20	1.869±0.13	2.041±0.12	2.991±0.17
<i>Penicillium expansum</i>	3.862±0.18	3.008±0.19	2.991±0.15	2.100±0.11
<i>Trichoderma viride</i>	4.751±0.22	2.751±0.15	1.006±0.04	3.121±0.19
<i>Trichoderma horzianum</i>	3.900±0.19	1.100±0.03	2.588±0.14	2.914±0.15
<i>Aspergillus terreus</i>	5.613±0.23	3.000±0.18	2.971±0.16	3.014±0.19

^a The values (average of triplicate) are diameter of zone of inhibition at 100 mg/mL crude extract and 30 µg/mL of (Amphotericin B; Fluconazol and Miconazole nitrate).

Figure 1: GC-MS chromatogram of methanolic extract of *Morganella morganii*.

Table 3: Zone of inhibition (mm) of test different bioactive compounds and standard antibiotics of medicinal plants to *Morganella morganii*.

S. No.	Plant	Zone of inhibition (mm)
2.	<i>Nerium olender</i> (Alkaloids)	4.03±0.21
5.	<i>Linum usitatissimum</i> (Crude)	4.92±0.23
6.	<i>Anastatica hierochuntica</i> (Crude)	6.00±0.25
7.	<i>Cassia angustifolia</i> (Crude)	5.05±0.24
8.	<i>Euphorbia lathyris</i> (Crude)	5.40±0.25
9.	<i>Rosmarinus officinalis</i> (Crude)	4.91±0.22
10.	<i>Mentha viridis</i> (Crude)	5.60±0.24
11.	<i>Quercus infectoria</i> (Crude)	5.00±0.22
12.	<i>Citrullus colocynthis</i> (Crude)	6.39±0.27
13.	<i>Althaea rosea</i> (Crude)	4.07±0.20
14.	<i>Coriandrum sativum</i> (Crude)	5.08±0.23
18.	<i>Ocimum basilicum</i> (Crude)	4.05±0.22
19.	<i>Punica granatum</i> (Crude)	5.00±0.22
22.	Control	0.00

Figure 2: Mass spectrum of Tricyclo[4.3.1.1(3,8)]undecan-1-amine with Retention Time (RT)= 3.150.

Figure 3: Mass spectrum of 3-Methoxybenzaldehyde semicarbazone with Retention Time (RT)= 3.396.

Figure 4: Mass spectrum of 3-Cyclohexene-1-carboxaldehyde, 1-methyl-, oxime, (Z)-(+)

Figure 5: Mass spectrum of 1-Decen-4-yne, 2-nitro- with Retention Time (RT)= 3.779.

Figure 6: Mass spectrum of 1,5,5-Trimethyl-6-methylene-cyclohexene with Retention Time (RT)= 3.996

Figure 7: Mass spectrum of 4-(2,5-Dihydro-3-methoxyphenyl)butylamine with Retention Time (RT)= 4.191

Figure 8: Mass spectrum of Paromomycin with Retention Time (RT)= 4.489

Figure 9: Mass spectrum of Benzenemethanol, 2-(2-aminopropoxy)-3-methyl- with Retention Time (RT)= 4.878

Figure 10: Mass spectrum of Acetamide, N-(6-acetylamino-2-thiazolyl)-2-(adamantan-1-yl)- with Retention Time (RT)= 4.986

Figure 11: Mass spectrum of Pterin-6-carboxylic acid with Retention Time (RT)= 5.759

Figure 12: Mass spectrum of 4-(2,5-Dihydro-3-methoxyphenyl)butylamine with Retention Time (RT)= 5.776

Figure 13: Mass spectrum of N-(2,5-Dicyano-3,4-dihydro-2H-pyrrrol-2-yl)-acetamide with Retention Time (RT)= 5.799

Figure 14: Mass spectrum of 3,10-Dioxatricyclo[4.3.1.0(2,4)]dec-7-ene with Retention Time (RT)= 5.822

Figure 15: Mass spectrum of 3-Cyclohex-3-enyl-propionic acid with Retention Time (RT)= 5.845

Figure 16: Mass spectrum of Eicosanoic acid, phenylmethyl ester with Retention Time (RT)= 6.348

Figure 17: Mass spectrum of 3,7-Diazabicyclo[3.3.1]nonane, 9,9-dimethyl- with Retention Time (RT)= 6.566

Figure 18: Mass spectrum of Dithiocarbamate , S-methyl-,N-(2-methyl-3-oxobutyl)- with Retention Time (RT)= 6.817

Figure 19: Mass spectrum of dl-Homocysteine with Retention Time (RT)= 7.813

Figure 20: Mass spectrum of 2-(2-Furyl)pyridine with Retention Time (RT)= 7.933

Figure 21: Mass spectrum of 1,7-Dioxo-10-thia-4,13-diazacyclopentadeca-5,9,12-trione with Retention Time (RT)= 9.003

Figure 22: Mass spectrum of 5,7-Dodecadiyn-1,12-diol with Retention Time (RT)= 9.438

Figure 23: Mass spectrum of 1-(β-d-Arabinofuranosyl)-4-O-difluoromethyluracil with Retention Time (RT)= 12.528

Figure 24: Mass spectrum of Uric acid with Retention Time (RT)= 12.814

Figure 25: Mass spectrum of Pyrrolo[1,2-a]pyrazine-1,4-dione, hexahydro- with Retention Time (RT)= 13.295

Figure 26: Mass spectrum of 12-Methyl-oxa-cyclododecan-2-one with Retention Time (RT)= 14.033

Figure 27: Mass spectrum of Phthalic acid, butyl undecyl ester with Retention Time (RT)= 14.067

Figure 28: Mass spectrum of 9,12,15-Octadecatrienoic acid, 2,3-bis(acetyloxy)propyl ester with Retention Time (RT)= 14.245

Figure 29: Mass spectrum of 1,2,4-Trioxolane-2-octanoic acid 5-octyl-, methyl ester with Retention Time (RT)= 14.565

Figure 30: Mass spectrum of 12-Dimethylamino-10-oxododecanoic acid with Retention Time (RT)= 14.948

Figure 31: Mass spectrum of Octahydrochromen-2-one with Retention Time (RT)= 15.343

Figure 32: Mass spectrum of L-Aspartic acid, N-glycyl- with Retention Time (RT)= 15.452

Figure 33: Mass spectrum of 2H-Oxecin-2-one, 3,4,7,8,9,10-hexahydro-4-hydroxy-10-methyl- with Retention Time (RT)= 15.532

Figure 34: Mass spectrum of Thiazolo[4,5-d]pyrimidine-5,7(4H,6H)-dione, 2-amino-4-(2-phenyl-) with Retention Time (RT)= 15.921

Figure 35: Mass spectrum of Dec-9-en-6-oxo-1-ylamide with Retention Time (RT)= 16.087

Figure 36: Mass spectrum of 3,6,12-Trimethyl-1,4,7,10,13,16-hexaaza-cyclooctadecane with Retention Time (RT)= 16.465

Figure 37: Mass spectrum of 2-Iodo-histidine with Retention Time (RT)= 16.682

Figure 38: Mass spectrum of 2,5-Piperazinedione, 3,6-bis(2-methylpropyl)- with Retention Time (RT)= 17.477

Figure 39: Mass spectrum of 9-Octadecenamide, (Z)- with Retention Time (RT)= 17.907

Figure 40: Mass spectrum of 3',8,8'-Trimethoxy-3-piperidyl-2,2'-binaphthalene-1,1',4,4'-tetra with Retention Time (RT)= 20.018

bacteremia, Kim found that 64% were related to intra-abdominal infections (included biliary infection, liver abscess and peritonitis)¹⁹. They can be separated from *Proteus* species by the lack of swarming activity or gelatin liquefaction or H₂S production. *Morganella* species can ferment mannose and have the enzyme ornithine decarboxylase which *Proteus* lack²⁰⁻²⁴. Initial therapy for patients with suspected bacteremia due to *Morganella* should be selected on the basis of local susceptibility patterns. A third-generation cephalosporin has been suggested as the drug of choice for *Morganella* infections²⁵⁻²⁷. UTI's due to *Morganella* should be treated with oral quinolones like ciprofloxacin.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Growth conditions and determination of metabolites

Morganella morganii strain was isolated from bronchitis patients and obtained from Maternity and children hospital. Subcultures were obtained on the nutrient agar for 48 hrs. at 22°C. The mixture was incubated at 4°C for 10 min and then shook for 10 min at 130 rpm.

Metabolites was separated from the liquid culture and evaporated to dryness with a rotary evaporator at 45°C. The residue was dissolved in 1 ml methanol, filtered through a 0.2 µm syringe filter, and stored at 4°C for 24 h before being used for GC-MS²⁸⁻³². The identification of the components was based on comparison of their mass spectra with those of NIST mass spectral library as well as on comparison of their retention indices either with those of authentic compounds or with literature values. The studied fungi, *Microsporium canis*, *Candida albicans*, *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, *Penicillium expansum*, *Trichoderma viride*, *Trichoderma horzianum*, and *Aspergillus terreus* were isolated and maintained in potato dextrose agar slants. Spores were grown in a liquid culture of potato dextrose broth (PDB) and incubated at 25°C in a shaker for 16 days at 130 rpm. The extraction was performed by adding 25 ml methanol to 100 ml liquid culture in an Erlenmeyer flask after the infiltration of the culture³³.

Materials of Plants Collection and Preparation

In this study, the leaves were dried at room temperature for ten days and when properly dried the leaves were powdered using clean pestle and mortar, and the powdered plant was size reduced with a sieve³⁴. The fine powder was then packed in airtight container to avoid the effect of humidity and then stored at room temperature.

Spectral analysis of bioactive natural chemical compounds of *Morganella morganii* using (GC/MS)

Analysis was conducted using GC-MS (Agilent 789 A) equipped with a DB-5MS column (30 m×0.25 mm i.d., 0.25 µm film thickness, J&W Scientific, Folsom, CA). The oven temperature was programmed as for the previous analysis. Helium was used as the carrier gas at the rate of 1.0 mL/min. Effluent of the GC column was introduced directly into the source of the MS via a transfer line (250 C°). Ionization voltage was 70 eV and ion source temperature was 230 C°. Scan range was 41-450 amu. The components were identified by comparing

their retention times to those of authentic samples of WILEY MASS SPECTRAL DATA BASE Library³¹⁻³⁵.

Determination of antibacterial and antifungal activity

Five-millimeter diameter wells were cut from the agar using a sterile cork-borer, and 25 µl of the samples solutions *Nerium olender* (Alkaloids), *Linum usitatissimum* (Crude), *Anastatica hierochuntica* (Crude), *Cassia angustifolia* (Crude), *Euphorbia lathyris* (Crude), *Rosmarinus officinalis* (Crude), *Mentha viridis* (Crude), *Quercus infectoria* (Crude), *Citrullus colocynthis* (Crude), *Althaea rosea* (Crude), *Coriandrum sativum* (Crude), *Ocimum basilicum* (Crude) and *Punica granatum* (Crude) were delivered into the wells. The plates were incubated for 48 h at room temperature. Antimicrobial activity was evaluated by measuring the zone of inhibition against the test microorganisms. Methanol was used as solvent control. Amphotericin B and fluconazole were used as reference antifungal agent [36-40]. The tests were carried out in triplicate. The antifungal activity was evaluated by measuring the inhibition-zone diameter observed after 48 h of incubation.

Data analysis

All the measurements were replicated three times for each assay and the results are presented as mean ± SD and mean ± SE. IBM SPSS 20 version statistical software package was used for statistical analysis of percentage inhibition and disease incidence and disease severity in each case.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Gas chromatography and mass spectroscopy analysis of compounds was carried out in methanolic extract of *Morganella morganii*, shown in Table 1. The GC-MS chromatogram of the twenty nine one peaks of the compounds detected was shown in Figure 1. Peaks were determined to be Tricyclo[4.3.1.1(3.8)]undecan-1-amine, 3-Methoxybenzaldehyde semicarbazone, carboxaldehyde, 1-methyl-,oxime ,(Z)-(+), 1,5,5-Trimethyl-6-methylene-cyclohexene, 4-(2,5-Dihydro-3-methoxyphenyl)butylamine, Paromomycin, 9-Borabicyclo[3.3.1]nonane, 9-mercapto-, Benzenemethanol, 2-(2-aminopropoxy)-3-methyl, Acetamide, N-(6-acetylaminobenzothiazol-2-yl)-2-(adamantan, rin-6-carboxylic acid, 4-(2,5-Dihydro-3-methoxyphenyl)butylamine, N-(2,5-Dicyano-3,4-dihydro-2H-pyrrol-2-yl)-acetamide, 3,10-Dioxatricyclo [4.3.1.0(2,4)]dec-7-ene, 3-Cyclohex-3-enyl-propionic acid, Eicosanoic acid, phenylmethyl ester, 3,7-Diazabicyclo[3.3.1]nonane, 9,9-dimethyl-, Dithiocarbamate, S-methyl-,N-(2-methyl-3-oxobutyl)-, dl-Homocysteine, 2-(2-Furyl)pyridine, 1,7-Dioxa-10-thia-4,13-diazacyclopentadeca-5,9,12-trione, 5,7-Dodecadiyn-1,12-diol, 1-(β-d-Arabinofuranosyl)-4-O-difluoromethyluracil, Uric acid, Pyrrolo[1.2-a]pyrazine-1,4-dione, hexahydro-,12-Methyl-oxa-cyclododecan-2-one, Phthalic acid, butyl undecyl ester, 9,12,15-Octadecatrienoic acid, 2,3-bis(acetyloxy)propyl ester, 1,2,4-Trioxolane-2-octanoic acid 5-octyl-, methyl ester, 12-Dimethylamino-10-oxododecanoic acid,

Octahydrochromen-2-one, L-Aspartic acid, N-glycyl-, 2H-Oxecin-2-one, 3,4,7,8,9,10-hexahydro-4-hydroxy-10-meth, Thiazolo[4,5-d]pyrimidine-5,7(4H,6H)-dione, 2-amino-4-(2-ph, Dec-9-en-6-oxo-1-ylamide, 3,6,12-Trimethyl-1,4,7,10,13,16-hexaaza-cyclooctadecane, 2-lodohistidine, 2,5-Piperazinedione, 3,6-bis(2-methylpropyl)-, 9-Octadecenamide, (Z)-, 3',8,8'-Trimethoxy-3-piperidyl-2,2'-binaphthalene-1,1',4,4'-tetra Figure 2-40. The results of anti-fungal activity produced by *Morganella morganii* showed that the volatile compounds were highly effective to suppress the growth of *Aspergillus terreus*. *Morganella morganii* produce many important secondary metabolites with high biological activities. Based on the significance of employing bioactive compounds in pharmacy to produce drugs for the treatment of many diseases, the purification of compounds produced by *Morganella morganii* can be useful. Maximum zone formation against *Aspergillus terreus* (5.613±0.23) mm, Table 2.

In agar well diffusion method the selected medicinal plants were effective against *Staphylococcus aureus*, Table 3. *Citrullus colocynthis* (Crude) was very highly active (6.39±0.27) mm against *Morganella morganii*. *Morganella morganii* was found to be sensitive to all test medicinal plants and mostly comparable to the standard reference antifungal drug Amphotericin B and fluconazole to some extent. Recently, it was demonstrated that volatile organic compounds (VOCs) of bacteria such as terpenoids, phenylpropanoids and fatty acid derivatives can influence the growth of some fungi and, in general, the inter- and intra-organismic communication signals.

CONCLUSION

Thirty nine bioactive chemical constituents have been identified from methanolic extract of the *Morganella morganii* by gas chromatogram mass spectrometry (GC-MS). In vitro antifungal and antibacterial evaluation of secondary metabolite products of *Morganella morganii* forms a primary platform for further phytochemical and pharmacological investigation for the development of new potential antimicrobial compounds.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

I am thankful to Dr. Imad Altae and head of department of biology Dr. Ali for helping me through the various analysis stages.

REFERENCES

1. Acar, J.F., Goldstein, F.W. Trends in bacterial resistance to fluoroquinolones. *Clin Infect Dis*. 1997;24 (1):S67-732.
2. Arranz-Caso JA, Cuadrado-Gomez LM, Romanik-Cabrera J, Garcia-Tena J. Pyomyositis caused by *Morganella morganii* in a patient with AIDS. *Clin Infect Dis* 1996;22:372-373.
3. Barnaud G, Arlet G, Danglot C, Philippon A. Cloning and sequencing of the gene encoding the AmpC β -lactamase of *Morganella morganii*. *FEMS Microbiol Letters* 1997;148:15-20.
4. Barroso H, Freitas-Vieira A, Duarte A. Molecular characterization of a Ceftazidime-Resistant *Morganella morganii* isolate producing a TEM-10 β -lactamase. *Antimicrob Agents Chemother* 1999;43:434-435.
5. Bush K, Jacoby GA, Medeiros AA. A functional classification scheme for beta-lactamases and its correlation with molecular structure. *Antimicrob Agents Chemother* 1995;39:1211-1233.
6. Chou YY, Chiu SK, Lai HC, Chang FY. Tubo-ovarian abscess with *Morganella morganii* bacteremia. *J Microbiol Immunol Infect*. 2009;42:357-9.
7. Croxatto A, Prod'hom G, Greub G. Applications of MALDI-TOF mass spectrometry in clinical diagnostic microbiology. *FE MS Microbiol Rev*. 2012;36:380-407.
8. Coudron PE, Moland ES, Sanders CC. Occurrence and detection of extended-spectrum β -lactamases in members of the family *Enterobacteriaceae* at a veterans affair medical center: seek and you may find. *J Clin Microbiol* 1997;35:2593-2597.
9. Custović A, Hadzić S. Epidemiology of bacterial intrahospital infections in newborns]. *Med Arh*. 2008;62(5-6):294-7.
10. del Mar Tavio M, Vila J, Ruiz J, Manuel Martin Sanchez A, Teresa Jimenez de Anta M. Decreased permeability and enhanced proton-dependent active efflux in the development of resistance to quinolones in *Morganella morganii*. *Int J Antimicrob Agents*. 2000;14:157-160.
11. DiPersio JR, Krafczyk TL. In vitro activity of netilmicin, gentamicin, tobramycin and amikacin against glucose fermenting and nonfermenting bacteria. *Chemotherapy* 1980;26:323.
12. Emery CL, Weymouth LA. Detection and clinical significance of extended-spectrum β -lactamases in a tertiary-care medical center. *J Clin. Microbiol*. 1997;35:2061-2067.
13. Emonet S, Shah HN, Cherkaoui A, Schrenzel J. Application and use of various mass spectrometry methods in clinical microbiology. *Clin Microbiol Infect*. 2010;16:1604-13.
14. Falagas ME, Kavvadia PK, Mantadakis E, Kofteridis DP, Bliziotis IA, Saloustros E, Maraki S, Samonis G *Morganella morganii* infections in a General Tertiary Hospital. *Infection*. 2006;34:315-321.
15. Fuchs PC, Barry AL, Sewell DL. Antibacterial activity of WY-49605 compared with those of the other oral agents and selection of disk content for disk diffusion and susceptibility testing. *Antimicrob Agents Chemother*. 1995;39:1472-1479.
16. Gebhart-Mueller Y, Mueller P, Nixon B. Unusual case of postoperative infection caused by *Morganella morganii*. *J Foot Ankle Surg*. 1998;37:145-147.
17. Haddad J Jr, Inglesby TV Jr, Addonizio L. Head and neck infections in pediatric cardiac transplant patients. *Ear Nose Throat J*. 1995;74:422-425.
18. Isaacs RD, Ellis-Pegler RB. Successful treatment of *Morganella morganii* meningitis with

- pefloxacinmesylate. *J Antimicrob.Chemother.* 1987;20:769-770.
19. Isobe H, Motomura K, Kotou K, Sakai H, Satoh M, Nawata H. Spontaneous bacterial empyema and peritonitis caused by *Morganella morganii*. *J Clin. Gastroenterol* 1994;18:87- 88.
 20. Jean SS, Hsueh PR, Lee WS, Yu KW, Liao CH, Chang FY. Carbapenem susceptibilities and non-susceptibility concordance to different carbapenems amongst clinically important Gram-negative bacteria isolated from intensive care units in Taiwan: results from the Surveillance of Multicentre Antimicrobial Resistance in Taiwan (SMART) in 2009. *Int J Antimicrob Agents.* 2013;41:457-62.
 21. Jensen KT, Frederiksen W, Hickman-Brenner FW, Steigerwalt AG, Riddle CG, Brenner DJ. Recognition of *Morganella* subspecies, with proposal of *Morganella morganii* subsp.morganii subsp.nov. and *Morganella morganii* subsp. Sibonii subsp. Nov. *Int J SystBacteriol.* 1992;42:613-620.
 22. Johnson JR, Feingold M. Case of chorioamnionitis in an immunocompetent woman caused by *Morganella morganii*. *J Maternal-fetal Med.* 1998;7:13-14.
 23. Katz LM, Lewis RJ, Borenstein DG. Successful joint arthroplasty following *Proteus morganii* (*Morganella morganii*) septic arthritis: a four-year study. *Arthritis Rheum* 1987;30:583-585.
 24. Kaye KS, Cosgrove S, Harris A, Eliopoulos GM, Carmeli Y. Risk factors for emergence of resistance to broad-spectrum cephalosporins among *Enterobacter* spp. *Antimicrob Agents Chemother.* 2001;45:2628-30.
 25. Kim BN, Kim NJ, Kim MN, Kim YS, Woo JH, Ryu J. Bacteremia due to tribe *Proteeae*: a review of 132 cases during a decade (1991-2000). *Scand J Infect Dis.* 2003;35: 98-103.
 26. Koyuncu Ş, Ozan F. *Morganella morganii* osteomyelitis complicated by secondary septic knee arthritis: a case report. *Acta Orthop Traumatol Turc.* 2012;46: 464-7.
 27. Krebs VL, Koga KM, Diniz EM, Ceccon ME, Vaz FA. Necrotizing fasciitis in a newborn infant: a case report. *Rev Hosp Clin Fac Med Sao Paulo* 2001;56:59-62.
 28. Kadhim MJ, Mohammed GJ, Hameed IH. In vitro antibacterial, antifungal and phytochemical analysis of methanolic fruit extract of *Cassia fistula*. *Oriental Journal of Chemistry.* 2016; 32(2): 10-30.
 29. Altameme HJ, Hameed IH, Idan SA, Hadi MY. Biochemical analysis of *Origanum vulgare* seeds by fourier-transform infrared (FT-IR) spectroscopy and gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS). *Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytotherapy.* 2015; 7(9): 221-237.
 30. Hussein HM. Determination of phytochemical composition and ten elements content (CD, CA, CR, CO, FE, PB, MG, MN, NI AND ZN) of *CARDARIA DRABA* by GC-MS, FT-IR and AAS technique. *Int. J Pharm Bio Sci.* 2016; 7(3): (B) 1009–1017.
 31. Hussein HM. Analysis of trace heavy metals and volatile chemical compounds of *Lepidium sativum* using atomic absorption spectroscopy, gas chromatography-mass spectrometric and fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy. *Research Journal of Pharmaceutical, Biological and Chemical Sciences.* 2016; 7(4): 2529 – 2555.
 32. Hameed IH. A new polymorphic positions discovered in mitochondrial DNA hypervariable region HVIII from central and north-central of Iraq. *Mitochondrial DNA.* 2016; 27(5): 3250-4.
 33. Sosa AA, Bagi SH, Hameed IH. Analysis of bioactive chemical compounds of *Euphorbia lathyris* using gas chromatography-mass spectrometry and fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy. *International Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemical Research.* 2016; 8(5): 109-126.
 34. Altameme HJ, Hadi MY, Hameed IH. Phytochemical analysis of *Urtica dioica* leaves by fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy and gas chromatography-mass spectrometry. *Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytotherapy.* 2015; 7(10): 238-252.
 35. Mohammed GJ, Omran AM, Hussein HM. Antibacterial and Phytochemical Analysis of *Piper nigrum* using Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrum and Fourier-Transform Infrared Spectroscopy. *International Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemical Research.* 2016; 8(6): 977-996.
 36. Hamza LF, Kamal SA, Hameed IH. Determination of metabolites products by *Penicillium expansum* and evaluating antimicrobial activity. *Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytotherapy.* 2015; 7(9): 194-220.
 37. Jasim H, Hussein AO, Hameed IH, Kareem MA. Characterization of alkaloid constitution and evaluation of antimicrobial activity of *Solanum nigrum* using gas chromatography mass spectrometry (GC-MS). *Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytotherapy.* 2015; 7(4): 56-72.
 38. Hadi MY, Mohammed GJ, Hameed IH. Analysis of bioactive chemical compounds of *Nigella sativa* using gas chromatography-mass spectrometry. *Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytotherapy.* 2016; 8(2): 8-24.
 39. Hameed IH, Ibraheem IA, Kadhim HJ. Gas chromatography mass spectrum and fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy analysis of methanolic extract of *Rosmarinus officinalis* leaves. *Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytotherapy.* 2015; 7 (6): 90-106.
 40. Shareef HK, Muhammed HJ, Hussein HM, Hameed IH. Antibacterial effect of ginger (*Zingiber officinale*) roscoe and bioactive chemical analysis using gas chromatography mass spectrum. *Oriental Journal of Chemistry.* 2016; 32(2): 20-40.